

The contribution of psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation to raising the performance level of football players for teams competing for promotion.

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Abstract

The study aims to identify the contribution of psychological preparation, cognitive preparation, and emotional preparation in enhancing the performance level of football players on teams competing for promotion. For this purpose, we used a descriptive method on a sample of 30 players from the senior team of Mouloudia Saïda, chosen randomly. To collect data, we used a tool to measure the reality of psychological preparation for national teams. After gathering and statistically processing the results, it was found that psychological preparation contributes to improving players' performance, followed by cognitive preparation and emotional preparation. Based on this, the study recommended the need for comprehensive training for players and the development of psychological skills, along with enhancing self-confidence and acquiring necessary motor skills.

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I. Introduction

Sports training has witnessed a remarkable development at the global level, and this development is also due to the developed countries' familiarity with the sports aspect in order to achieve a high level in the sports aspect and raise the level of performance to reach excellence and excellence in multiple scientific ways.

Football is undoubtedly the most popular sport in the world, which has prompted club managers to make great efforts to attract the best and most experienced coaches and sign the most prominent players. In general, the coaching process in football aims to improve the level of performance in skill, psychological, tactical, technical, mental and emotional aspects. As far as the emotional aspect is concerned, it is an essential part of a person's life and relates to their behaviour and personality, which varies from one individual to another. Some individuals possess emotional maturity and adaptability, while others lack this ability and face difficulties in compatibility and coexistence (Aboul-Nasr, 2008, p. 36).

Athletes are remarkably similar in terms of physical and technical abilities, but there is a decisive factor that affects the results of their efforts during sports competitions in order to achieve victory, which is the psychological factor, which plays a major role in achieving success. (Mohammed Hassan Allawi, 1978, p. 26)

Mental preparation is a vital element in sport, as it contributes to athletes' understanding of different situations, their creativity in performance, and their excellence in their sporting aspects. Therefore, psychological, cognitive, and emotional preparation should be given great importance due to their effective role in the sports field, and none of them can be dispensed with. Rihana's (2019) study also indicated that the lack of psychological preparation negatively affects the results of sports teams, which calls for the need to focus on psychological preparation and the use of a psychologist to diagnose and treat psychological conditions that may affect the performance of players.

Hence, our study was characterised by the general question and the following sub-questions:

1General Question:

- What is the contribution of psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation in maximising the performance of football players for teams competing for promotion?

1.1Sub-questions:

- Does psychological preparation contribute to increasing the level of performance of football players of teams competing for promotion?

- Does cognitive preparation contribute to increasing the level of performance of footballers in promotion-competitive teams?

- Does emotional preparation contribute to the level of performance of footballers in promotion-competitive teams?

- Importance of the study:

- Expanding the scope of research into the reality of psychological preparation in football for teams seeking promotion.

- Enhancing scientific knowledge by increasing players' awareness of the importance of psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation.

- Psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation is one of the most important training indicators that directly affect the sports preparation process, especially in football for teams competing for promotion.

__ Previous studies:

The first study: By the researcher "Tawfiq Qaqa'aa" in 2022, entitled " 'The place and role of psychological preparation in raising the level of performance of handball players under the age of 17 from the point of view of some coaches.' This study sought to explore the impact of psychological preparation on the performance of handball players from the point of view of coaches. The researcher adopted a descriptive approach and applied a questionnaire measuring aspects of psychological preparation to a sample of 15 coaches. The results of the study showed that psychological preparation plays a vital role in achieving results, as there is a clear relationship between psychological preparation and physical, technical and tactical factors. The study also found the importance of taking into account the psychological characteristics of the age group (juniors) and the psychological pressures they face, in addition to the necessity of having an

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experienced psychologist for each team to achieve a high level of performance.

The second study: ‘Sharaf Mohammed Amin 2023’, entitled: “The effectiveness of psychological preparation on the athletic performance of football players during the competition phase”. The effectiveness of psychological preparation on the athletic performance of football players during the competition phase’, this study aims to evaluate the effect of psychological preparation on the athletic performance of football players during competitions. The results revealed that the aim of psychological preparation is to enhance the level of athletes' performance during competition, and that it has a positive impact on the overall performance of the players during the competition period.

Search terms:

Psychological preparation:

It is the educational procedures using methods that aim to minimise the negative effects of arousal on sports performance. It also supports the appropriate conditions and situations in the sports field, which helps in reducing psychological burdens, thus reducing feelings of pressure, stress and anxiety, and enhancing self-confidence, which reflects positively on the level of sports achievement (Tariq and Ahmed, 2001, p. 214). Procedurally, it is all the steps determined by the coach and sports psychologist to enhance volitional qualities and develop moral values in players.

Cognitive preparation:

Knowledge is the foundation on which the athlete's development is based, as it plays a vital role in the building process, as enhancing knowledge positively affects the improvement of scientific and practical abilities. These abilities mean that the athlete must use his mind and intelligence in implementing tactical plans and trying to recognise tactical mistakes that he may make (Mohamed Osman, 1987, p. 224). In procedural terms, it is to maximise the athletic level of the players by enhancing the theoretical understanding and mastering it better.

Emotional preparation: Emotions are internal states that reflect multiple cognitive aspects, including sensations, physiological reactions and specific expressive behaviour, and appear suddenly in a variety of forms that are difficult to control. (Mohammed Hassan, 1994, p. 245). Procedurally, it

refers to the methods adopted by the individual to deal with disturbing emotional stimuli during the execution of a particular task, so that they are reduced to a level that allows them to continue with their daily activities without any disturbance or negative impact on their behaviour or performance.

Sports performance:

It is defined by Dr Essam Abdul Khaliq as ‘Sports performance is : It is a reflection of the abilities and motivations of each individual for the best possible behaviour as a result of the reciprocal effects of internal force and is often performed individually.

Procedurally, it refers to the ability of athletes to achieve outstanding results in their fields and reach a certain level of achievement.

Methodological procedures:

Exploratory study: The exploratory study was carried out with the following objectives:

1. Checking the efficiency of the research tools and their compatibility with the study sample.
2. Reviewing a set of books, studies and previous research that dealt with the variables related to the current study (psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation and sports performance).
3. Understanding the method and method used in applying the research tool (electronic questionnaire).

The main study:

Methodology of the study: The descriptive method was used as it suits the nature of the study

Population and study sample:

Study population: The study population consisted of football players.

The study sample: The study sample consisted of 30 players of the Mouloudia Saida senior team, whose number was estimated at 30 players selected randomly.

Research areas:

Temporal domain: The main study was conducted from 15 June 2024 to 05 July 2024.

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Human domain: The human domain consisted of the Mouloudia Saida senior team

Identifying the study variables:

Independent variable: psychological, cognitive, and emotional preparation.

The dependent variable: sports performance.

The study tools: The study tools consisted of a scale of the reality of psychological preparation among national teams by the researcher (Jahan Awad, 2022), which consisted of three axes (psychological, cognitive, and emotional preparation), and the number of phrases amounted to 30 phrases. Its scientific foundations were studied through the external consistency method (retesting). The correlation coefficient of the scale was calculated as (0.829) at the level of significance (0.01), from which it can be said that the scale has a good level of stability, i.e. valid to measure what it was designed to measure.

The statistics used: After the results were collected, they were downloaded and statistically processed using the spss package using the following methods:

- Mean, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages

- Presentation and discussion of results:

Present and discuss the results of the first hypothesis: that psychological preparation contributes to increasing the performance of football players of teams competing for promotion.

Table 01: The frequencies, percentages, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, order of the paragraphs and the rank of each of them for the first axis (psychological preparation contributes to raising the level of performance of football players of teams competing for promotion).

Phrases of the first axis (psychological preparation)	Scale	I agree	Somewhat	Disagree	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	Number of points	Rank
01	Frequency	22	08	00	2,73	0,45	82	01
	(Percentages %)	73,3	26,7	00				
02	Frequency	12	18	00	2,40	0,49	72	06
	(Percentages %)	40	60	00				
03	Frequency	18	10	02	2,53	0,62	76	03
	(Percentages %)	60	33,3	6,7				
04	frequency	13	06	11	2,07	0,90	62	05
	(Percentages %)	43,3	20	36,7				
05	frequency	11	05	14	1,90	0,92	57	07
	(Percentages %)	36,7	16,7	46,7				
06	frequency	04	11	15	1,63	0,71	49	08
	(Percentages %)	13,3	36,7	50				
07	frequency	16	07	07	2,30	0,83	69	04
	(Percentages %)	53,3	23,3	23,3				
08	frequency	19	08	03	2,53	0,68	76	02
	(Percentages %)	63,3	26,7	0				
09	frequency	22	08	00	2,73	0,45	82	01
	(Percentages %)	73,3	26,7	00				
10	frequency	18	09	03	2,50	0,68	75	03
	(Percentages %)	60	30	10				

We notice from Table No. (01) that the responses of the research sample confirmed that mental preparation contributes to the performance of football players in teams competing for promotion, as the percentage of affirmative responses ranges between (13.3% // 73.3%). It is clear that the psychological aspect is the main influence on performance during competition. It is essential to pay attention to the psychological aspect just like the physical and skill aspects. Players are disturbed by the club's lack of concern in providing a sports psychologist for the players, and they sometimes feel the need for someone who understands their psychological state before, during, and after competition, as they only receive help from their coach in acquiring information related to psychological aspects and developing psychological skills through a specialized training program. They do not have anyone to turn to for alleviating the psychological burden after a defeat, and they sometimes find that the decline in their performance is due to their shortcomings in psychological preparation for the match.

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Presentation and discussion of the results of the second hypothesis: that cognitive preparation contributes to improving the performance level of soccer players from teams competing for promotion.

Table. 02: Represents the frequencies, percentages, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and ranking of the items, along with their rank regarding the second axis (cognitive preparation contributes to improving the performance level of soccer players from teams competing for promotion).

Phrases of the first axis (psychological preparation)	Scale	I agree	Somewhat	Disagree	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	Number of points	Rank
11	Frequency	05	09	19	1,53	0,77	46	07
	(Percentages %)	7,16	20	3,63				
12	Frequency	07	13	10	1,90	0,75	57	06
	(Percentages %)	3,23	3,43	3,33				
13	Frequency	20	09	01	2,63	0,55	79	04
	(Percentages %)	66,7	30	3,3				
14	frequency	20	08	02	2,60	0,62	78	04
	(Percentages %)	66,6	26,7	6,7				
15	frequency	27	03	00	2,90	0,30	87	01
	(Percentages %)	90	10	00				
16	frequency	21	06	03	2,60	0,67	78	03
	(Percentages %)	70	20	10				
17	frequency	16	09	03	2,73	0,76	71	05
	(Percentages %)	53,3	30	16,7				
18	frequency	24	05	01	2,77	0,50	83	02
	(Percentages %)	80	16,7	3,3				
19	frequency	20	07	03	2,57	0,67	77	04
	(Percentages %)	66,7	23,3	10				
20	frequency	21	06	03	2,60	0,67	78	03
	(Percentages %)	70	20	10				

We notice from table number (02) that the responses of the research sample individuals confirmed that cognitive preparation contributes to the performance of football players on teams competing for promotion, with the percentage of agreement responses ranging between (16.7% // 90%). It is evident that players are able to maintain their attention focus and continue performing despite the superiority of the opponent, and their practice of

mental imagery for skills enhances their attention focus, which they do right before entering the competition. The psychological preparation program helps them acquire motor skills, at a rate of (70%), and they can control the negative thoughts they face before entering the competition.

Presentation and discussion of the results of the third hypothesis: which states that emotional preparation contributes to improving the performance level of soccer players in teams competing for promotion.

Table No. 03: Represents the frequencies, percentages, mean, standard deviation, and the ranking of the paragraphs and their rank concerning the third axis (Emotional preparation contributes to improving the performance level of football players in teams competing for promotion).

Phrases of the first axis (psychological preparation)	Scale	I agree	Somewhat	Disagree	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	Number of points	Rank
21	Frequency	23	06	01	2,73	0,52	82	03
	(Percentages %)	76,7	20	3,3				
22	Frequency	22	06	02	2,67	0,60	80	04
	(Percentages %)	73,3	20	6,7				
23	Frequency	23	07	00	2,77	0,43	83	03
	(Percentages %)	76,7	23,3	00				
24	frequency	25	05	00	2,83	0,37	85	01
	(Percentages %)	83,3	16,7	00				
25	frequency	21	07	02	2,63	0,61	79	05
	(Percentages %)	70	23,3	6,7				
26	frequency	08	13	09	1,97	0,76	59	08
	(Percentages %)	26,7	43,3	30				
27	frequency	09	09	12	1,90	0,84	57	07
	(Percentages %)	30	30	40				
28	frequency	25	01	04	2,70	0,70	81	01
	(Percentages %)	83,3	3,3	13,3				
29	frequency	10	12	08	2,07	0,78	62	06
	(Percentages %)	33,3	40	26,7				
30	frequency	24	05	01	2,77	0,50	83	02
	(Percentages %)	80	16,7	3,3				

We note from Table No. (03) that the responses of the research sample individuals confirmed that emotional preparation contributes to the

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performance of football players on teams competing for promotion, as the percentage of agreement responses ranges between (26.7% - 83.3%). It became clear to us that players have clear emotional goals, and they insist on achieving victory despite the pressures of competition. They are always able to achieve their goals under the pressures of competition, and they do not lose confidence in themselves when faced with competitive pressures, no matter how intense. They can manage negative thoughts that confront them before the start of the competition and adjust their performance. Sometimes they feel the need for continuous monitoring of their psychological state before the competition.

Discussion:

Discussion of the 1st hypothesis:

Through Table No. (01), it is evident that psychological preparation significantly contributes to enhancing the performance level of football players on teams competing for promotion, with an average reaching (2.73) and a standard deviation of (0.92). This indicates that the level of importance of this axis is high, reflecting the contribution of psychological preparation and confirming the results of the first hypothesis, which states that psychological preparation contributes to improving the performance level of football players on teams competing for promotion. It also confirms that most negative results are due to the lack of a psychological preparator in the club, and demonstrates that psychological preparation contributes to acquiring motor skills and enhances self-confidence.

Discussion of the 2nd hypothesis:

From Table No. (02), it is clear that cognitive preparation contributes significantly to improving the performance level of football players in teams competing for promotion, with a mean reaching (2.77) and a standard deviation of (0.77). This indicates that the level of importance for this axis is high, reflecting the contribution of cognitive preparation and confirming the results of the second hypothesis, which states that cognitive preparation contributes to enhancing the performance level of football players in teams competing for promotion. It also confirms that cognitive preparation helps maintain attention focus and ensures continuity in performance, as it plays a major role in mental visualization before entering the competition directly.

Discussion of the 3rd hypothesis:

Through Table No. (03), it is evident that emotional preparation contributes significantly to enhancing the performance level of football players in teams

competing for promotion, with an average reaching (2.83) and a standard deviation of (0.84). This indicates that the level of importance for this aspect is high, reflecting the contribution of emotional preparation and confirming the results of the third hypothesis, which states that emotional preparation contributes to improving the performance level of football players in teams competing for promotion. It also confirms that good emotional preparation reduces competition pressure and helps in building self-confidence.

Based on the study, the various aspects of which were addressed through presentation, analysis and discussion, a set of results were reached, most notably:

- Good psychological preparation enhances players' desire to improve their sports performance and contributes to the acquisition of motor skills.
- The need to qualify coaches psychologically and make them aware of the importance of this aspect.
- Players recognise the importance of the psychological aspect in their sporting career and their desire to receive psychological support, in addition to their dissatisfaction with the club's lack of psychological facilities.
- Many of the negative results are due to the absence of a psychologist.
- The importance of focusing on the cognitive and mental side of the players.
- Good emotional preparation alleviates the pressure of competition and boosts self-confidence.
- Psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation complement each other and play a major role in improving the performance of footballers in teams competing for promotion.

Conclusion :

Through the study that we conducted, and after reviewing its various scientific, methodological and statistical aspects, it is clear that psychological, cognitive and emotional preparation plays an important role in improving the level of performance of football players in teams competing for promotion. We confirmed this by proving the first, second and third hypotheses, in addition to confirming the general hypothesis of the study in a field and statistical manner. This indicates the importance of each of these aspects in enhancing sports performance to achieve the best results, as well as preparing players comprehensively and developing their psychological skills. It also requires controlling players' emotions before,

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during, and after competition, while enhancing self-confidence and acquiring the necessary motor skills.

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The annexes:

وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
 جامعة الجزائر3
 معهد التربية البدنية والرياضية
 قسم: التدريب الرياضي

إستمارة إستبيان موجهة للاعبين فريق مولودية سعيدة

من إعداد ط. د. : بن ويس عبد المومن
 تحية طيبة وبعد:

في إطار التحضير لإعداد مقال علمي بعنوان: مكانة التحضير النفسي في كرة القدم للفرق المنافسة على الصعود (من وجهة نظر اللاعبين) نطلب من سيادتكم المحترمة التكرم بالإجابة على أسئلتنا قصد مساعدتنا على إنجاز هذا المقال العلمي للتوصل إلى نتائج تنفيذ الدراسة. ونعلمكم أن إجاباتكم تبقى سرية ولا تستخدم إلا لغرض البحث العلمي و شكرا لكم .

رقم الفقرة	العبارة	أوافق	إلى حد ما	لا أوافق
01	أعلم أن الجانب النفسي هو المؤثر الرئيسي في أدائي أثناء المنافسة			
02	أجد أن هبوط مستواي ناتج عن قصور في إعدادي النفسي للمباراة			
03	يساعدني مدربي في معرفة المعلومات المرتبطة بالجوانب النفسية			
04	لا أجد من ألجأ إليه لتخفيف العبء النفسي عند الهزيمة			
05	لست راضي عن إعتبار مدربي بأن التحضير النفسي من الأمور الثانوية في إعداد اللاعبين			
06	يهتم مدربي بالجوانب البدنية و المهارية و يهمل الجانب النفسي			
07	يساعدني مدربي في إكتساب المهارات النفسية من خلال برنامج تدريبي خاص بها			
08	يزعجني عدم إهتمام النادي بتوفير أخصائي نفسي رياضي للاعبين			
09	أرى أنه من الضروري الإهتمام بالجانب النفسي مثله مثل الجانب البدني و المهاري			
10	أحيانا أشعر أنني في حالة إلى من يتفهم حالتي النفسية قبل و أثناء و بعد المنافسة			
11	أفقد التفكير بإيجابية قبل الدخول في المنافسة			
12	يتشنت إنتباهي عند التعرض لضغوط المنافسة			
13	أستطيع السيطرة على الأفكار السلبية التي تواجهني قبل الدخول في المنافسة			
14	لدي أفعال إنفعالية واضحة أريد تحقيقها			
15	أستطيع المحافظة على تركيز أنتباهي و الإستمرار في الأداء رغم تفوق المنافس			

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